

Ionization Constants of some Heterocyclic Carboxylic Acids having Analytical Possibilities

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The ionization constants of nine heterocyclic carboxylic acids have been determined by potentiometric titration and are being compared with those available in literature. Three among these viz., 3-chloro-quinoxaline-2-carboxylic acid, 3-hydroxy-quinoxaline-2-carboxylic acid and 3-hydroxy picolinic acid are being reported for the first time.

Heterocyclic carboxylic acids are for long known to be good chelating agents, as a result, much investigations have been carried out on their metal complexes mostly for analytical purposes. Mentions may be made of analytical uses of picolinic acid¹, quinaldinic acid², quinoline 8-carboxylic acid³, pyridine 2:3 dicarboxylic acid⁴. The solubility products and complexity constants of various metal quinaldinates have also been evaluated by Flagg⁵ and Lumme⁶.

Several other reagents of similar type having quinoxaline ring instead of quinoline ring are now being suggested and expected to be similarly good analytical reagents. Quinoxaline 2-carboxylic acid which appears to be iso-electronic with quinaldinic acid and several of its derivatives with substitution at the 3-position by -chloro, -hydroxyl and another carboxyl group, which will definitely have some effects on the properties of the parent acid e.g. in solubility and ionization behaviour as well as their reactivity towards metal ions are now being tried.

Before proceeding with the actual application of these reagents for analytical purpose it has been found desirable to determine the accurate values of the ionization constants of these acids which are much needed for this purpose. The values of some of these acids have already been determined by few workers, these have been redetermined and placed together with ours for comparison.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used viz. sodium perchlorate, perchloric acid, caustic soda etc. were G.R.E.M. quality.

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2. P. Rây and co-workers, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1933, **95**, 400; *Mikrochemie*, 1935 **17**, 11; *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1939, **115**, 265; *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1935, **100**, 324.
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5. J. F. Flagg, *Organic reagents used in gravimetric and volumetric analysis*, Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1948, p. 247.
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Picolinic acid(I): This was synthesized in the laboratory from α -picoline by the method of Dyson and Hammick⁷ and purified by vacuum sublimation. (m.p. 131°, lit. 130-132°).

Quinaldinic acid (II): Prepared from quinaldine by Hammick's⁸ method, recrystallised from glacial acetic acid and dried at 120°. m.p. 157°, lit. 157°).

Quinoline-8-carboxylic acid (III): purchased from N.C.L. (Poona), India. The compound was recrystallised from water by boiling with active charcoal. (m.p. 186°, lit. 185-186°).

Quinoxaline-2-carboxylic acid (IV): This compound was synthesized by the method of Maurer and Boettger⁹. m.p. 210° (decomp) lit. 210° (decomp.)

3 chloro quinoxaline-2-carboxylic acid (V): Prepared according to the method of Gowenlock et. al.¹⁰ m.p. 146° (decomp.), lit. 146-147°.

3-hydroxy quinoxaline-2-carboxylic acid (VI)¹⁰ (m.p. 263°, lit. 263-265°).

3-hydroxy picolinic acid hydrochloride(VII): This compound was kindly supplied by Dr. John T. Sheehan¹ of Squibb Research Institute, New Brunswick, U.S.A. (m.p. 218-220°).

Pyridine-2:3-dicarboxylic acid (VIII): Prepared by the oxidation of oxine with fuming nitric acid¹², purified by repeated recrystallisation from water. (m. p. 192-195°, lit. 192-194°).

Quinoxaline-2:3-dicarboxylic acid (IX): This was synthesized in the laboratory according to the method of Chattaway and Humphrey¹³. Purified by recrystallisation from water. (m.p. 189° (decomp.), lit. 190° (decomp.)).

The purities of the compounds were checked by determining their neutralization equivalents and the experimental values were found to be in good agreement with theoretical one.

Potentiometric titration:

The ionization constants of the acids mentioned, were determined by potentiometric titration with standard alkali and for determining the $K_{a, H}^a$ values standard perchloric acid were used. The reagent solutions prepared were of strength varying from $2 \times 10^{-2} M$ to $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ depending on their water solubilities. All measurements were performed at a constant initial ionic strength of $0.1 M$ which was maintained by adding requisite quantity of sodium perchlorate; a constant temperature too were maintained by placing the titration cell in an electrically regulated thermostat maintained at a temperature $25 \pm 0.2^\circ$.

7. P. Dyson and D. LL Hammick, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 781 (1939).

8. D. LL. Hammick, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 2882 (1923).

9. K. Maurer and B. Boettger, *Ber.*, 1938, **B71**, 1383.

10. A. H. Gowenlock, G. T. Newbold, F. S. Spring, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 622,

11. J. T. Sheehan, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 636.

12. E. Sucharda, *Ber.*, 1925, **58B**, 1727.

13. F. D. Chattaway and W. G. Humphrey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 647.

pH measurements were done with a Cambridge pH meter (bench type) which gives values accurate upto 0.02 pH unit. The pH meter was standardised before use, and checked after each titration with buffer solutions of pH 4.00 and 9.27. Electrode systems consisted of glass electrode (pH range 1-13) and reference electrode as saturated calomel electrode.

The results reported here are based on duplicate titrations made under identical conditions which were reproducible with maximum variation of ± 0.02 pH unit.

Solubility method:

Speakman's¹⁴ original method was used with slight modification. Several series of saturated solutions of compound (IV) in suitable buffer solutions of pH varying from 1-4 were equilibrated at 25° for several hours; ionic strength of the solutions were maintained at 0.1M by adding sodium perchlorate. Solutions were then filtered dry and the reagent concentration was estimated as its copper salt*, corresponding pH of the solutions were recorded by the pH meter.

TABLE I

Reagent	Our values		Literature values.
	Pk ^a H	Pk ^a ₂	
I. Picolinic acid	1.03±0.05	5.30±0.01	1.60, 5.44 ^a , 1.01, 5.32 ^b ; 5.23; 1.03 5.33 ^d ; 1.5, 5.43 ^e ; 1.07, 5.25 ^f
II. Quinaldinic acid	1.45±0.05	4.91±0.01	1.90, 4.92 ^e ; 1.30*, 4.97 ^g ; 4.92 ^h
III. Quinoline-8-carboxylic acid	2.01±0.03	6.84	1.80, 6.87 ^b , 2.00, 6.71 ^e ; 2.0, 6.76 ⁱ
IV. Quinoxaline-2-carboxylic acid	2.80±0.01, 2.76 (solubility method)		2.875±0.011 ^j
V. 3-chloro quinoxaline-2-carboxylic acid	1.83±0.02		—
	Pk ^a ₁	Pk ^a ₂	
VI. 3-hydroxy quinoxaline-2-carboxylic acid	2.58±0.02	9.43±0.01	—
VII. 3-hydroxy picolinic acid	5.17±0.01	10.76±0.01	—
VIII. Pyridine, 2:3-dicarboxylic acid	2.43±0.01	4.78±0.01	2.36, 4.72 ^k
IX. Quinoxaline, 2:3-dicarboxylic acid	1.80±0.02	3.31±0.02	1.62, 3.64 ^j

(a) K. Suzuki and K. Yamaski, *Naturwiss*, 1957, **44**, 396. (b) R. W. Green and H. K. Tong, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 4896. (c) G. Anderegg, *Helv. chim. Acta*, 1960, **43**, 414. (d) P. O. Lumme, *Soumen Kem.*, 1958, **31B**, 250. (e) F. Holmes and W. R. C. Crippin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 1175, 3467. (f) L. Moyne and G. Thomas, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1964, **31**, 583. (g) P. O. Lumme, Thesis, *Ann. Acad. Sci. Fennicae.*, 1955, **II**, **68**, 7. *Calculated value (h) P. E. Wenger, D. Monnier, and L. Spars, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1952, **35**, 396, 569 (i) M. Yasuda—Personal communication to A. E. Martel, Stability constants of metal ion complexes. Special publication 17, London, the Chemical Society 1964. (j) W. F. Gum and M. M. Joulle, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1965, **30**, 3982 (k) M. Yasuda and K. Yamaski, *Naturwiss*, 1958, **45**, 84.

*It has been observed that copper is precipitated quantitatively from its solution even in strong acid medium (Authors, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, in press).

14. J. C. Speakman, *ibid.*, 1940, 855.

The results given in the table were calculated by the conventional half \bar{n} method, of Block and McIntyre¹⁵, curve fitting¹⁶ and in the cases of compound VIII and IX also by the Noyes method¹⁷. In all cases the spread of error has been evaluated.

DISCUSSION

The values available in the literature for the ionization constants of picolinic acid are numerous. Pk_{IH}^a ranges from 1.00-1.50 and Pk_2^a from 5.20-5.50. The values reported by Lumme^d, Green *et al.*^b, Moyne and Thomas^f nicely agree with our values.

The Pk_2^a value of quinaldinic acid is in good agreement with the values of previous workers. Holmes *et al.*^e reported $Pk_{IH}^a=1.90$ and Lumme could not determine this step of ionization experimentally, though he gave a calculated value for this stage Pk_{IH}^a as 1.30.

The Pk_{IH}^a of quinoline-8-carboxylic acid reported by Holmes *et al.* is the same as obtained by us, however, their Pk_2^a value differs from ours which agree well with that of Lumme^g.

For quinoxaline-2-carboxylic acid the value obtained by Gum and Julie^j is higher by 0.075 unit over our value. Concordant values were obtained by us applying two different methods.

The two Pk values of pyridine 2-3 dicarboxylic acid obtained by us differ by +0.07 unit from those reported by Yama and Yamaski^k.

The Pk values of quinoxaline 2:3-dicarboxylic acid as obtained by us seriously disagree with those of Julie *et al.*^j We have subjected our experimental results to various methods of calculation and obtained the close values.

The Pk values of other acid (V, VI and VII) have been determined for the first time.

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